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BR11894–R–R–R–R–169: A COLD-TOLERANT BREEDING LINE FOR DRY SEASON TO MITIGATE THE EARLY FLASH FLOOD DAMAGE IN THE HAOR AREAS OF BANGLADESH

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Abstract

Early flash floods in the *Haor*, a basin-like wetlands, in Bangladesh, routinely damage the dry season (*Boro*) rice cultivation. Heavy rainfall and Meghalayan hill water surges from the India cause flash flooding every three to four years here. Since the *Boro* rice is the main crop, this flash flood threatened the food security of the *Haor* peoples. It should be planted between the last week of October and the first week of November, instead of the usual 15th of November, so that it could be harvested by the end of March, before the flash flood. Because the reproductive stage of rice falls between the 4th week of January and 1st week of February, such early sowing always causes cold damage. Rice, a tropical or subtropical plant, is cold-sensitive, especially during the booting stage, when pollen abortion and immature microspore malformation cause spikelet sterility and hamper rice yield. Cold temperatures during the reproductive period reduce rice production in *Haor* areas by degenerating spikelets, partially exserting panicles, and increasing spikelet sterility. Breeding cold-tolerant rice varieties helps prevent flash floods and cold harm. With this aim, one rice breeding line, BR11894–R–R–R–R–169 has been developed. After three years (2020–2023) of on-farm evaluation at 10 *Haor* locales, it was observed the line flowered from 09–24 February and the

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and BR11894-R-R-R-169) produced 5.8–6.4 t/ha in 140–151 days. The results suggest for advancing this line to the proposed variety trial. Thus, BR11894-R-R-R-169 will be getting approval to release as a cold-tolerant new variety for *Haor* areas of Bangladesh to mitigate early flash flood damage of *Boro* rice.

Theme

Fast-tracking genetic solutions and varieties